

Supplemental Material for “Topology in the Random Scattering of Light”

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In this supplemental material, we provide details on the effective field theory for light scattering from random media.

In this supplemental material, we closely follow the analysis presented in Ref. [1] regarding strongly disordered Weyl semimetals. We highlight differences in 3d light scattering due to the presence of longitudinal and transverse modes, referring to the former for further details when the distinctions are not significant. For notational convenience, we set the vacuum speed of light $c = 1$. Additionally, to ensure this supplemental material is self-contained, we repeat some of the content from the ‘Methods’ section of the main text.

REPLICA FIELD THEORY

Following our discussion in the main text we first concentrate on an inhomogeneous refractive index and homogeneous impedance (‘dual limit’), and in a second step include variations of the latter (‘helicity mixing’). The complex interference processes underlying Anderson localization manifest on length scales exceeding the mean free path. Their description is most efficiently formulated in terms of the diffusion modes of the disordered system. Specifically, interference processes can be organized in terms of diffusion modes scattering off each other, and corresponding interaction vertices are encoded in a nonlinear sigma-model. Starting point of the field theory description is the replica partition function,

$$\mathcal{Z}[j] = \int D\psi \left\langle e^{i \int d^3x \bar{\psi} (i\delta\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} + \omega - \tau_3 \otimes \not{k} - V - j)\psi} \right\rangle_V, \quad (1)$$

where $\psi = \{\psi_{s,\sigma,a,\nu,\chi}(\mathbf{x})\}$ is a $(2 \times 2 \times R \times 3 \times 2)$ component Grassmann field. Here $s = 1, 2$ is a two-component index distinguishing between retarded and advanced indices, $\sigma = 1, 2$ has been introduced to account for time-reversal symmetry of the class AI system, $a = 1, \dots, R$ is a replica index, $\nu = 1, 2, 3$ parametrizes the spin-1 degree of freedom, $\chi = \pm$ is the helicity, and $\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} = \delta_{ss'}(-1)^{s+1}$ a Pauli matrix causing infinitesimal symmetry breaking in the advanced-retarded sector. Time-reversal symmetry manifests in the relation $\bar{\psi} = (i\sigma_2^{\text{tr}}\psi)^T$, with σ_2^{tr} acting in the space of time-reversal indices $\sigma = 1, 2$. Differentiation of Eq. (1) with respect to the source j , generates ensemble averages of products of retarded and advanced Green’s functions entering e.g. the inverse participation ratio I_2 defined in the main text [2, 3]. We here do not consider j further, but notice that it can be chosen structureless in helical τ -space.

We next summarize the key construction steps underlying the nonlinear sigma-model: The action in Eq. (1) is invariant under uniform rotations $\psi \rightarrow T\psi$ commuting with $\tau_3 \otimes \not{k}$. That is, homogeneous rotations that are structureless in spin-indices $\nu = 1, 2, 3$, and diagonal in helical τ -space. We also notice that $T^T = \sigma_2^{\text{tr}}T^{-1}\sigma_2^{\text{tr}}$ to guarantee the time-reversal symmetry constraint on $\bar{\psi}, \psi$. Averaging over Gaussian fluctuations of the light potential generates a ψ^4 -contribution, local in space and non-local in ‘internal’ indices s, σ, a, ν, χ . The latter is decoupled by a matrix field, playing the role of a self-energy, via Hubbard-Stratonovich transformation. Integration over ψ leads to a representation of \mathcal{Z} entirely in the matrix field, which is subjected to a stationary point analysis. The SCBA self-energy of the previous paragraph provides a saddle point, consistent with causality of the theory. The physics on long length scales is encoded in soft rotations around the latter, $i\kappa T\sigma_3T^{-1}$, and corresponding soft mode action is derived from a ‘trace-log’ expansion. We next detail the above outlined construction steps.

EFFECTIVE ACTION

Hubbard-Stratonovich decoupling and mean-field analysis

Starting out from the replica partition function Eq. (1), the Gaussian average over fluctuations $V_{\mathbf{x}}$ results in a quartic ‘interaction term’, that is decoupled by a matrix-field via Hubbard-Stratonovich transformation,

$$\langle e^{i \int d^3x \bar{\psi} V \psi} \rangle_V = e^{-\frac{w}{2} \int d^3x \bar{\psi} \psi \bar{\psi} \psi} = \int dQ e^{-\frac{1}{2w} \text{Tr} Q^2 + \int d^3x \bar{\psi} Q \psi}. \quad (2)$$

Integration over $\bar{\psi}, \psi$, then gives the alternative representation of the partition function in terms of the matrix-field $Z = \int dQ e^{-S[Q]}$, with

$$S[Q] = \frac{1}{2w} \text{Tr} Q^2 - \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \ln (\omega - \tau_3 \otimes \not{k} + i\delta\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} - j + iQ), \quad (3)$$

where the factor 1/2 reflects that $\bar{\psi}, \psi$ are dependent variables. Variation of the action leads to the saddle point equation,

$$Q = \frac{iw}{2} \int (dk) \frac{1}{\omega - \tau_3 \otimes \not{k} + i\delta\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} + iQ}, \quad (4)$$

where we neglected the source j , and introduced $(dk) \equiv d^3k/(2\pi)^3$. We then focus on the simplest real solution, noting that a finite imaginary part can be absorbed by a renormalization of ω . Inserting the ansatz $Q = \kappa\sigma_3^{\text{ra}}$, dictated by causality, we arrive at

$$\kappa = -\frac{w}{2} \text{Im} \int (dk) \left(\frac{2}{3} \frac{\omega + i\kappa}{(\omega + i\kappa)^2 - k^2} + \frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{\omega + i\kappa} \right), \quad (5)$$

which is the Dyson equation for the (imaginary part of the) self-energy in the self-consistent Born approximation. As stated in the main text, we here keep things simple and only consider identical self-energies for transverse and longitudinal modes. Generalization to different self-energies is straightforward, but does not change our main conclusions (see also main text). Integrals Eq. (5) are formally UV divergent, which is related to the approximation of uncorrelated spatial fluctuations $w(x) = w\delta(x)$. A model with uncorrelated spatial fluctuations is only reasonable when the photon wave length $1/\omega$ exceeds the actual correlation length of fluctuations, and a cut-off Λ thus has to be introduced. The solution κ then depends on the ratios of w, ω , and Λ . For our purposes, however, it is sufficient to continue with an unspecified general κ .

Soft mode action and trace-log expansion

Parametrizing fluctuations as rotations of the meanfield solution $Q = \kappa T \sigma_3 T^{-1}$ we first notice that soft rotations are diagonal in helical space, $T = \text{diag}(T_+, T_-)$. This reflects the presence of two independent helical diffusion modes in the dual scattering limit. The effective action controlling the low energy partition function is then a sum of contributions from the two helical modes, $Z = \int D[T_+, T_-] e^{-S[T_+] - S[T_-]}$, with

$$S[T_\chi] = -\frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \ln (\omega_0 - \chi \not{k} + i\kappa T_\chi \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} T_\chi^{-1}). \quad (6)$$

Similarity transformation under the ‘trace-log’, $\text{Tr} \ln(\dots) \rightarrow \text{Tr} \ln(T_\chi^{-1}(\dots)T_\chi)$, then leads to an expression in terms of $\mathcal{A}_\chi \equiv S_i A_{\chi,i} \equiv S_i T_\chi^{-1} \partial_i T_\chi$, which can be exposed to a gradient-expansion. However, to apply the transformation, we need to account for UV-divergencies typical for Dirac-like operators. Following the regularization scheme of Refs. [1, 4] this leads to

$$S[T_\chi] = -\frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \ln (\omega + i\kappa\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} - \chi \not{k} - i\chi \mathcal{A}_\chi) - S_\eta[T_\chi], \quad (7)$$

where $S_\eta[T_\chi] = \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \ln (i\eta\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} - \chi \not{k} - i\chi \mathcal{A}_\chi)$ with $\eta \rightarrow 0$ is introduced to regularize divergencies. We then identify the inverse SCBA Green’s function, $G_\chi^{-1} = \omega + i\kappa\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} - \chi \not{k}$, and expose the action to a gradient expansion of the trace-log

to third order in $G_\chi \mathcal{A}_\chi$. For simplicity, we now concentrate on the helical +-mode, drop the helical index χ , and obtain results for the helical --mode from parity transformation $\mathbf{k} \mapsto -\mathbf{k}$. We will see that for the expansion to order $n \leq 3$, a decomposition in transverse and longitudinal components of the Green's function gives

$$\text{tr}([G\mathcal{A}]^n) = \text{tr}((1 - n\bar{\pi}_\mathbf{k})[G_t\mathcal{A}]^n) + n\text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_\mathbf{k}G_l\mathcal{A}[G_t\mathcal{A}]^{n-1}), \quad (8)$$

with

$$G_k^s = G_{t,k}^s \pi_\mathbf{k} + G_{l,k}^s \bar{\pi}_\mathbf{k}, \quad G_{t,k}^s = N_k^s (\omega_s + \not{k}), \quad G_{l,k}^s = \frac{1}{\omega_s}, \quad (9)$$

where $\omega_s = \omega + i s \kappa$ and $N_k^s = (\omega_s^2 - k^2)^{-1}$. Specifically, for $n = 3$ we will find that $\bar{\pi}_\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} \mathbb{1}_3$ in the first term, implying that

$$\text{tr}([G\mathcal{A}]^3) = 3\text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_\mathbf{k}G_l\mathcal{A}[G_t\mathcal{A}]^2). \quad (10)$$

That is, only triangle graphs involving one longitudinal and two transverse modes contribute, as stated in the main text.

Linear order

The first order expansion in $G\mathcal{A}$ can be organized as,

$$S^{(1)} = -\frac{i}{2} \text{tr}(G\mathcal{A}) = S_0^{(1)} + S_1^{(1)}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$S_0^{(1)} = -\frac{i}{2} \sum_s f_i^s \int d^3x \text{tr}(P^s A_i), \quad f_i^s = \int (dk) \text{tr}(G_k^s S_i), \quad (12)$$

$$S_0^{(2)} = \frac{i}{2} \sum_s f_{ik}^{ss} \int d^3x \text{tr}(P^s A_k A_i), \quad f_{ik}^{ss} = -\frac{i}{2} \int (dk) \text{tr}(G_k^s S_k G_k^s S_i), \quad (13)$$

and we employed that $\partial_{x_k} A_i = -A_k A_i$ and $\partial_{k_i} G_k^s = G_k^s S_i G_k^s$.

Second order

To second order expansion of the trace-log in $G\mathcal{A}$,

$$S^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{4} \text{tr}(G\mathcal{A}G\mathcal{A}) = S_0^{(2)} + S_1^{(2)}, \quad (14)$$

with

$$S_0^{(2)} = -\frac{1}{4} \sum_{ss'} f_{ss'}^{ij} \int d^3x \text{tr}(P^s A_i P^{s'} A_j), \quad f_{ss'}^{ij} = \int (dk) \text{tr}(G_k^s S_i G_k^{s'} S_j), \quad (15)$$

$$S_1^{(2)} = \frac{i}{4} \sum_{ss'} f_{ss'}^{ijk} \int d^3x \text{tr}(P^s [\partial_{x_k} A_i] P^{s'} A_j), \quad f_{ss'}^{ijk} = \int (dk) \text{tr}([\partial_{p_k} G_k^s] S_i G_k^{s'} S_j). \quad (16)$$

Third order

To third order expansion of the trace-log in $G\mathcal{A}$,

$$S^{(3)} = \frac{i}{6} \text{tr}(G\mathcal{A}G\mathcal{A}G\mathcal{A}), \quad (17)$$

where for our purposes it is sufficient to approximate,

$$S_0^{(3)} = \frac{i}{6} \sum_{s_1 s_2 s_3} f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} \int d^3x \text{tr}(P^{s_1} A_i P^{s_2} A_j P^{s_3} A_k), \quad f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = \int (dk) \text{tr}(G_k^{s_1} S_i G_k^{s_2} S_j G_k^{s_3} S_k). \quad (18)$$

Traces

We next perform traces, using that

$$\text{tr}(S_i S_j S_k) = i\epsilon_{ijk}, \quad \text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} S_i S_j S_k) = \frac{i}{3}\epsilon_{ijk}, \quad \text{tr}(S_i \not{k} S_j \not{k} S_k) = \frac{ik^2}{3}\epsilon_{ijk}, \quad \text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} S_i \not{k} S_j \not{k} S_k) = \frac{ik^2}{3}\epsilon_{ijk}. \quad (19)$$

We further employ low order expansions of Moyal products of functions A and B depending only on coordinates, respectively, momenta

$$(AB)(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{k}) = A(\mathbf{x})B(\mathbf{k}) + \frac{i}{2}\partial_{\mathbf{x}}A(\mathbf{x})\partial_{\mathbf{k}}B(\mathbf{k}) + \dots, \quad (20)$$

$$(BA)(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{k}) = A(\mathbf{x})B(\mathbf{k}) - \frac{i}{2}\partial_{\mathbf{x}}A(\mathbf{x})\partial_{\mathbf{k}}B(\mathbf{k}) + \dots. \quad (21)$$

It is convenient to start with the expression resulting from the third order trace-log expansion and then turn to the second and first order contributions.

Third order term

Separating different contributions from longitudinal and transverse modes, we introduce

$$f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = \int (dk) \left(f_{ijk,tt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} + f_{ijk,lt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} \right), \quad (22)$$

$$f_{ijk,tt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = \text{tr} \left((1 - 3\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}}) G_{t,k}^{s_1} S_i G_{t,k}^{s_2} S_j G_{t,k}^{s_3} S_k \right), \quad f_{ijk,lt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = 3\text{tr} \left(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} G_{l,k}^{s_1} A_i G_{t,k}^{s_2} S_j G_{t,k}^{s_3} S_k \right), \quad (23)$$

where the factor three in $3\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}}$ in the last term sums the three contributions related by symmetrization under cyclic exchange of (s_1, i) , (s_2, j) , and (s_3, k) . We then find that

$$f_{ijk,tt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = 0, \quad (24)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f_{ijk,lt}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} &= 3\text{tr} \left(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} G_{l,k}^{s_1} S_i G_{t,k}^{s_2} S_j G_{t,k}^{s_3} S_k \right) \\ &= \frac{3}{\omega_{s_1}} N_k^{s_2} N_k^{s_3} (\omega_{s_2} \omega_{s_3} \text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} S_i S_j S_k) + \text{tr}(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} S_i \not{k} S_j \not{k} S_k)) \\ &= \frac{i\epsilon_{ijk}}{\omega_{s_1}} N_k^{s_2} N_k^{s_3} (\omega_{s_2} \omega_{s_3} + k^2), \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

leading to

$$f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = \frac{i\epsilon_{ijk}}{\omega_{s_1}} \int (dk) N_k^{s_2} N_k^{s_3} (\omega_{s_2} \omega_{s_3} + k^2). \quad (26)$$

Notice that upon symmetrization under cyclic exchange of (s_1, i) , (s_2, j) ,

$$f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3} = \frac{i}{3}\epsilon_{ijk} \int (dk) \left(N_k^{s_2} N_k^{s_3} \frac{\omega_{s_2} \omega_{s_3} + k^2}{\omega_{s_1}} + N_k^{s_3} N_k^{s_1} \frac{\omega_{s_3} \omega_{s_1} + k^2}{\omega_{s_2}} + N_k^{s_1} N_k^{s_2} \frac{\omega_{s_1} \omega_{s_2} + k^2}{\omega_{s_3}} \right). \quad (27)$$

Second order term

Continuing with the term $S_0^{(2)}$ found in second order trace-log expansion, we write

$$f_{ss'}^{ij} = \int (dk) \left(f_{ss',tt}^{ij} + f_{ss',lt}^{ij} \right), \quad f_{ss',tt}^{ij} = \text{tr} \left((1 - 2\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}}) G_{t,k}^s S_i G_{t,k}^{s'} S_j \right), \quad f_{ss',lt}^{ij} = 2\text{tr} \left(\bar{\pi}_{\mathbf{k}} G_{l,k}^s S_i G_{t,k}^{s'} S_j \right), \quad (28)$$

and use that

$$\begin{aligned}
f_{ss',tt}^{ij} &= N_k^s N_k^{s'} \text{tr} \left((1 - 2\bar{\pi}_k) \omega_s S_i \omega_{s'} S_j + p_m^2 S_m S_i S_m S_j \right) \delta_{ij} \\
&= \frac{1}{3} N_k^s N_k^{s'} \text{tr} \left((\omega_s \omega_{s'} + k^2) S_i^2 \right) \delta_{ij} \\
&= \frac{2}{3} N_k^s N_k^{s'} (\omega_s \omega_{s'} + k^2) \delta_{ij},
\end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

and

$$f_{ss',lt}^{ij} = 2N_k^{s'} \text{tr} \left(\bar{\pi}_k G_{l,k}^s S_i \omega_{s'} S_j \right) = \frac{4\omega_{s'}}{3\omega_s} N_k^{s'} \delta_{ij}, \tag{30}$$

to arrive at

$$f_{ss'}^{ij} = 2 \int (dk) N_k^s N_k^{s'} \left(\omega_s \omega_{s'} + \frac{k^2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{2\omega_{s'}}{\omega_s} \right) \right). \tag{31}$$

For the contribution $S_1^{(2)}$, found in second order trace-log expansion, we notice that

$$\partial_{k_i} G_k^s = G_k^s S_i G_k^s, \tag{32}$$

and thus

$$f_{ss'}^{ijk} = \int (dk) \text{tr} \left(G_k^s S_k G_k^s S_i G_k^{s'} S_j \right) = f_{ijk}^{ss'}, \tag{33}$$

with $f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3}$ from the third order trace-log expansion calculated above.

First order term

First order terms vanish.

Integrations

For convenience, we summarize all relevant terms found above,

$$f_{ij}^{ss} = 2 \int (dk) N_k^s N_k^s \left(\omega_s \omega_s - \frac{k^2}{3} \right), \tag{34}$$

$$f_{ij}^{+-} + f_{ij}^{-+} = 4 \int (dk) N_k^+ N_k^- \left(\omega^2 + \kappa^2 + \frac{k^2}{3} - \frac{k^2 \omega^2 - \kappa^2}{3 \omega^2 + \kappa^2} \right), \tag{35}$$

$$f_{ijk}^{++-} = \frac{i}{3} \epsilon_{ijk} \int (dk) \left(2N_k^+ N_k^- \left(\omega_- + \frac{k^2}{\omega_+} \right) + N_k^+ N_k^+ \frac{\omega_+ \omega_+ + k^2}{\omega_-} \right), \tag{36}$$

$$f_{ijk}^{--+} = \frac{i}{3} \epsilon_{ijk} \int (dk) \left(2N_k^- N_k^+ \left(\omega_+ + \frac{k^2}{\omega_-} \right) + N_k^- N_k^- \frac{\omega_- \omega_- + k^2}{\omega_+} \right), \tag{37}$$

$$f_{ijk}^{+++} = i \epsilon_{ijk} \int (dk) N_k^+ N_k^+ \left(\omega_+ + \frac{k^2}{\omega_+} \right), \tag{38}$$

$$f_{ijk}^{---} = i \epsilon_{ijk} \int (dk) N_k^- N_k^- \left(\omega_- + \frac{k^2}{\omega_-} \right), \tag{39}$$

which are next evaluated using that

$$\int (dk) [N_k^s]^2 k^2 \rightarrow \frac{3is\omega_s}{8\pi}, \quad \int (dk) N_k^+ N_k^- k^2 \rightarrow \frac{\omega^2 - 3\kappa^2}{8\pi\kappa}, \quad \int (dk) [N_k^s]^2 = \frac{is}{8\pi\omega_s}, \quad \int (dk) N_k^+ N_k^- = \frac{1}{8\pi\kappa}, \tag{40}$$

where the first two integrals used regularization by S_η in the limit $\eta \rightarrow 0$, see Ref. [1] for further details.

We then find

$$f_{ij}^{ss} = 0, \quad f_{ij}^{+-} + f_{ij}^{-+} = \frac{(\omega^2 + 3\kappa^2)(\omega^2 - \frac{1}{3}\kappa^2)}{2\pi\kappa(\omega^2 + \kappa^2)}, \quad (41)$$

and

$$f_{ijk}^{++-} = \frac{i\epsilon_{ijk}}{6\pi} \left(\frac{\omega^2 - \kappa^2}{\kappa\omega_+} + \frac{i\omega_+}{\omega_-} \right), \quad f_{ijk}^{--+} = \frac{i\epsilon_{ijk}}{6\pi} \left(\frac{\omega^2 - \kappa^2}{\kappa\omega_-} - \frac{i\omega_-}{\omega_+} \right), \quad f_{ijk}^{+++} = -\frac{\epsilon_{ijk}}{2\pi}, \quad f_{ijk}^{---} = \frac{\epsilon_{ijk}}{2\pi}, \quad (42)$$

and notice that

$$f_{ijk}^{++-} + f_{ijk}^{--+} = 0. \quad (43)$$

Action

We now have all ingredients to derive the different contributions to the effective action.

First order

We first recall that first order terms vanish, $S_0^{(1)} = S_1^{(1)} = 0$.

First term from second order

The leading contribution from second order is,

$$S_0^{(2)} = -\frac{(\omega^2 + 3\kappa^2)(\omega^2 - \frac{1}{3}\kappa^2)}{32\pi\kappa(\omega^2 + \kappa^2)} \int d^3x \operatorname{tr} (A_i A_i - \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i). \quad (44)$$

Noting that $T[A_i, \sigma_3^{\text{ra}}]T^{-1} = \partial_i Q$, with $Q = T\sigma_3^{\text{ra}}T^{-1}$, this leads to the diffusive σ model action for the helical modes discussed in the main text.

Remaining contributions

The remaining second and third order term can be combined to

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^{(2)} + S_0^{(3)} &= -\frac{i}{4} f_{ijk}^{++-} \int d^3x \operatorname{tr} (P^+ A_i A_j P^- A_k - 2P^+ A_i P^+ A_j P^- A_k) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{4} f_{ijk}^{--+} \int d^3x \operatorname{tr} (P^- A_i A_j P^+ A_k - 2P^- A_i P^- A_j P^+ A_k) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{4} f_{ijk}^{+++} \int d^3x \operatorname{tr} \left(P^+ A_i A_j P^+ A_k - \frac{2}{3} P^+ A_i P^+ A_j P^+ A_k \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{i}{4} f_{ijk}^{---} \int d^3x \operatorname{tr} \left(P^- A_i A_j P^- A_k - \frac{2}{3} P^- A_i P^- A_j P^- A_k \right). \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

We then notice that in the above expression the first two contributions simplify to

$$\begin{aligned} &f_{ijk}^{++-} \operatorname{tr} (P^+ A_i A_j P^- A_k - 2P^+ A_i P^+ A_j P^- A_k) + f_{ijk}^{--+} \operatorname{tr} (P^- A_i A_j P^+ A_k - 2P^- A_i P^- A_j P^+ A_k) \\ &= -\frac{1}{4} (f_{ijk}^{++-} + f_{ijk}^{--+}) \operatorname{tr} (\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i A_j A_k - \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_j \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_k) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where to pass from the first to second line we used invariance of $f_{ijk}^{s_1 s_2 s_3}$ under cyclic permutations of i, j, k . The last two contributions, on the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_{ijk}^{+++} \text{tr} \left(P^+ A_i A_j P^+ A_k - \frac{2}{3} P^+ A_i P^+ A_j P^+ A_k \right) + f_{ijk}^{---} \text{tr} \left(P^- A_i A_j P^- A_k - \frac{2}{3} P^- A_i P^- A_j P^- A_k \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} f_{ijk}^{+++} \text{tr} \left(\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i A_j A_k - \frac{1}{3} \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_j \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_k \right), \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

where we used that $f_{ijk}^{---} = -f_{ijk}^{+++}$ and invariance under cyclic permutations of i, j, k . We thus arrive at the contribution,

$$S_1^{(2)} + S_0^{(3)} = -\frac{i\epsilon_{ijk}}{16\pi} \int d^3x \text{tr} \left(\sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i A_j A_k - \frac{1}{3} \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_i \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_j \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} A_k \right), \quad (48)$$

which, using $\epsilon_{ijk} A_j A_k = -\epsilon_{ijk} \partial_j A_k$, gives the Chern-Simons action discussed in the main text. Finally we notice that employing different self-energies for transverse and longitudinal modes modifies the coupling σ of the diffusive sigma model action, but does not modify the topological term within the accuracy of the weak disorder approximation $\kappa \ll \omega$.

Helicity mixing

Departing from the ‘dual limit’ we next add the helicity-mixing contribution $\tau_1 \phi_Z$ resulting from a locally varying impedance,

$$S_{\pm}[T] = -\frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \ln (\omega_0 + i\kappa \sigma_3^{\text{ra}} - \tau_3 \not{k} + \not{A}_Z), \quad (49)$$

where we introduced $\not{A}_Z \equiv T^{-1} \tau_1 \not{\phi}_Z T$, and dropped the contribution \not{A}_χ discussed in the previous section. Expansion of the ‘Tr ln’ to quadratic order we use $\langle a_{Z,i,\mathbf{x}} a_{Z,j,\mathbf{y}} \rangle = \gamma \delta_{ij} \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y})$, and arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\pm}[T] &= -\frac{\gamma}{4} \int d^3x \text{tr} (TG(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) T^{-1} \tau_1 S_i T G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) T^{-1} \tau_1 S_i) \\ &= \left(\frac{2\kappa}{w} \right)^2 \times \frac{3\gamma}{4} \int d^3x \text{tr} (Q \tau_1 Q \tau_1), \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where in passing from the first to the second line we employed the mean-field equation Eq. (5). Tracing over helical space we then arrive at the contribution coupling the two helical slow fields, discussed in the main text.

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- [1] Alexander Altland, and Dmitry Bagrets, “*Theory of the strongly disordered Weyl semimetal*”, Phys. Rev. B **93**, 075113 (2016).
 [2] Alexander D. Mirlin, “*Statistics of energy levels and eigenfunctions in disordered systems*”, Physics Reports **326**, 259 (2000).
 [3] K. B. Efetov, “*Synergism in Disorder and Chaos*”, Cambridge University Press (1997).
 [4] Alexander Altland, B.D. Simons and M.R. Zirnbauer, “*Theories of low-energy quasi-particle states in disordered d-wave superconductors*”, Physics Reports **359**, 283 (2002).